

NHST Student's t-Test Statistics

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1 Basic Test Statistics

1.1 Student's t-tests

1.2 One-sample t-test

Test whether the estimated mean of normally distributed random sample data differs from a known or hypothesised population mean.

$$t = \frac{\bar{x} - \mu_0}{s/\sqrt{n}} \quad \text{where} \quad \begin{cases} s \text{ is the sample standard deviation} \\ \mu_0 \text{ is the hypothesised population mean} \\ \bar{x} \text{ is the sample mean} \\ n \text{ is the sample size} \\ \text{the t-statistic is compared against t-distribution with } n - 1 \text{ dof} \end{cases}$$

Here we are getting the p-value for the hypothesised population mean whose cumulative probability distribution corresponds to the sampling distribution of the mean estimator for unknown σ i.e. how extreme is the observed data under the null hypothesis?

Theorem 1.1. pooled t-test test statistic *The pooled t-test statistic is given by:*

$$t = \frac{\bar{x} - \mu_0}{s/\sqrt{n}}$$

Proof. The data is drawn from a normal **population** distribution $X \sim N(\mu, \sigma^2)$ so from 2.10 variance of expectation:

$$\bar{X} \sim N\left(\mu, \frac{\sigma^2}{n}\right) \quad (\text{non-standardised})$$

Here the mean μ and the variance σ^2 is estimated (\bar{x} and s^2 respectively). Also we calculate the sample mean \bar{x} to calculate the numerator of the test statistic - taking the difference with the hypothesised population mean μ , therefore the mean estimate follows a bastardised student's t-distribution with the loss of one dof:

$$\bar{X} \sim t_{n-1}\left(\bar{x}, \frac{s^2}{n}\right) \quad (\text{bastardised})$$

More formally and helpfully we always standardise the statistic so under $H_0 : \mu = \mu_0$:

$$\frac{\bar{X} - \mu_0}{s/\sqrt{n}} \sim t_{n-1} \quad (\text{studentised})$$

□

1.3 Pooled t-test

Test *matching means* of two populations using two sets of sample data which is;

- independent
- identically normally distributed (or CTL applies for large n)
- both populations have **equal variance**

test statistic:

$$t_\nu = \frac{\bar{x} - \bar{y}}{\sqrt{\frac{s_p^2}{n_1} + \frac{s_p^2}{n_2}}} \quad \text{where} \quad \begin{cases} s_p \text{ is the pooled sample standard deviation} \\ \bar{x}, \bar{y} \text{ are the respective sample means} \\ n_1, n_2 \text{ are the respective sample sizes} \\ \text{the t-statistic is compared against t-distribution with } n_1 + n_2 - 2 \text{ dof} \end{cases}$$

pooled standard deviation:

$$s_p = \sqrt{\frac{(n_1 - 1)s_1^2 + (n_2 - 1)s_2^2}{n_1 + n_2 - 2}}$$

This test compares the means of two independent sets of samples, assuming the two populations are normally distributed with the same variance and different mean i.e. $X \sim N(\mu_1, \sigma)$ and $Y \sim N(\mu_2, \sigma)$. The test is called "pooled" because it combines (or pools) the sample variances to estimate a common variance.

We use the pooled t-test only if the normality assumption is met (or n is large — CLT), variances are equal (should be checked with an F-test or Levene's test). Otherwise, use Welch's t-test, which doesn't assume equal variances.

Theorem 1.2. pooled t-test test statistic *The pooled t-test statistic is given by:*

$$\frac{\bar{x} - \bar{y}}{s_p \sqrt{\frac{1}{n_X} + \frac{1}{n_Y}}} \sim t_{n_X + n_Y - 2} \quad \text{where} \quad s_p^2 = \frac{(n_X - 1)s_X^2 + (n_Y - 1)s_Y^2}{n_X + n_Y - 2}$$

Proof. The data is drawn from the **two populations** with matching variance:

$$X_1 \sim \mathcal{N}(\mu_X, \sigma^2) \quad \text{and} \quad Y_2 \sim \mathcal{N}(\mu_Y, \sigma^2)$$

note: the expectation variances won't match even under H_0 if dataset sizes differ...

$$\bar{x} \sim \mathcal{N}(\mu_1, \sigma^2/n_1) \quad \text{and} \quad \bar{y} \sim \mathcal{N}(\mu_2, \sigma^2/n_2) \quad \text{2.10 variance of expectation}$$

$$\boxed{\frac{\bar{x} - \mu_X}{s_X/\sqrt{n_X}} \sim t_{n_X - 1}} \quad \text{and} \quad \boxed{\frac{\bar{y} - \mu_Y}{s_Y/\sqrt{n_Y}} \sim t_{n_Y - 1}} \quad \text{(studentised distributions)}$$

The sampling distribution of the **mean difference estimator** has a similar form:

$$\mathbb{E}[\bar{x} - \bar{y}] = \mathbb{E}[\bar{x}] - \mathbb{E}[\bar{y}] = \mu' \quad \text{2.3 linearity of expectation}$$

$$\text{Var}[\bar{x} - \bar{y}] = \text{Var}[\bar{x}] + \text{Var}[\bar{y}] = \frac{\sigma^2}{n_X} + \frac{\sigma^2}{n_Y} \quad \text{2.9 variance of independent difference}$$

$$\therefore \mathbb{E}[\bar{x}] - \mathbb{E}[\bar{y}] \sim \mathcal{N}\left(\mu', \frac{\sigma^2}{n_X} + \frac{\sigma^2}{n_Y}\right) \quad \text{(population distribution)}$$

under $H_0 : \mu_X = \mu_Y$, and 2.3 linearity of expectation: $\hat{\mu}' = 0$ and using sample variance s_p :

$$\therefore \frac{\bar{x} - \bar{y} - \mu'}{\sqrt{\frac{s_p^2}{n_1} + \frac{s_p^2}{n_2}}} = \boxed{\frac{\bar{x} - \bar{y}}{\sqrt{\frac{s_p^2}{n_X} + \frac{s_p^2}{n_Y}}} \sim t_{n_X + n_Y - 2}} \quad \text{(studentised sampling distribution)}$$

The common variance estimated by the **pooled** sample variance s_p , this is just the weighted average of two sample variances of the populations x_1 and x_2 , again note that these may differ due to differing sample size even though the population variances match...

$$s_p^2 = \frac{(n_X - 1)s_X^2 + (n_Y - 1)s_Y^2}{n_X + n_Y - 2}$$

$$\frac{\bar{x} - \bar{y}}{s_p \sqrt{\frac{1}{n_X} + \frac{1}{n_Y}}} = \frac{\bar{x} - \bar{y}}{\text{SE}} \sim t_{n_X + n_Y - 2} \quad \text{where} \quad \text{SE} = \sqrt{s_p^2 \left(\frac{1}{n_X} + \frac{1}{n_Y} \right)} \quad \text{and}$$

Note to self, the degrees of freedom are $n_1 + n_2 - 2$ because we still explicitly calculate the estimated sample means \bar{x} and \bar{y} and therefore lose two degrees of freedom prior to estimating the pooled variance. □

1.4 Welch's t-test

Test *matching means* of two populations using two sets of sample data which is;

- independent
- identically normally distributed (or CTL applies for large n)
- both populations have **different variance**

(more common and safer than pooled t-test in practice)

$$t_\nu \sim \frac{\bar{x} - \bar{y}}{\sqrt{\frac{s_1^2}{n_1} + \frac{s_2^2}{n_2}}} \quad \text{where} \quad \begin{cases} s_1, s_2 \text{ are the respective sample standard deviations} \\ \bar{x}, \bar{y} \text{ are the respective sample means} \\ n_1, n_2 \text{ are the respective sample sizes} \\ \text{the t-statistic is compared against t-distribution with (typically) fractional dof (see below...)} \end{cases}$$

Welch-Satterthwaite approximation:

$$\nu = \frac{\left(\frac{s_1^2}{n_1} + \frac{s_2^2}{n_2} \right)^2}{\frac{\left(\frac{s_1^2}{n_1} \right)^2}{n_1 - 1} + \frac{\left(\frac{s_2^2}{n_2} \right)^2}{n_2 - 1}}$$

Theorem 1.3. Welch test statistic The Welch test statistic is given by:

$$t_\nu \sim \frac{\bar{x} - \bar{y}}{\sqrt{\frac{s_1^2}{n_1} + \frac{s_2^2}{n_2}}} \quad \text{where} \quad \nu = \frac{\left(\frac{s_1^2}{n_1} + \frac{s_2^2}{n_2} \right)^2}{\frac{\left(\frac{s_1^2}{n_1} \right)^2}{n_1 - 1} + \frac{\left(\frac{s_2^2}{n_2} \right)^2}{n_2 - 1}}$$

Proof. ...

1.4.1 Test Statistic

Data is drawn from two **populations with matching mean**, under H_0 :

$$\begin{aligned} X &\sim \mathcal{N}(\mu, \sigma_1^2) \quad \text{and} \quad Y \sim \mathcal{N}(\mu, \sigma_2^2) \\ \bar{x} &\sim \mathcal{N}(\mu, \sigma_1^2/n_1) \quad \text{and} \quad \bar{y} \sim \mathcal{N}(\mu, \sigma_2^2/n_2) \quad \text{2.10 variance of expectation} \\ \frac{\bar{x} - \mu}{s_1/\sqrt{n_1}} &\sim t_{n_1-1} \quad \text{and} \quad \frac{\bar{x} - \mu}{s_2/\sqrt{n_2}} \sim t_{n_2-1} \quad \text{(studentised sampling distributions)} \end{aligned}$$

The sampling distribution of mean difference estimator has a similar form:

$$\mathbb{E}[\bar{x} - \bar{y}] = \mathbb{E}[\bar{x}] - \mathbb{E}[\bar{y}] = 0 \quad \text{2.1 linearity of expectation}$$

$$\text{Var}[\bar{x} - \bar{y}] = \text{Var}[\bar{x}] + \text{Var}[\bar{y}] = \frac{\sigma_1^2}{n_1} + \frac{\sigma_2^2}{n_2} \quad \text{2.9 variance of independent sum}$$

$$\therefore \mathbb{E}[x_1] - \mathbb{E}[x_2] \sim \mathcal{N}\left(0, \frac{\sigma_1^2}{n_1} + \frac{\sigma_2^2}{n_2}\right) \quad (\text{mean difference sampling distribution under } H_0)$$

the **two variance estimates are coupled**, so in estimating both we lose a fractional dof as well as two more for the necessary sample mean estimates:

$$\therefore \boxed{\frac{\bar{x} - \bar{x}_2}{\sqrt{\frac{\sigma_1^2}{n_1} + \frac{\sigma_2^2}{n_2}}} \sim t_\nu} \quad (\text{welch -test statistic})$$

estimating the dof is really the key to this test statistic...

1.4.2 Degrees of Freedom

The test statistic is a function of sampling distributions for sample variance of the two groups... *i.i.d. sample variance estimator has a chi-squared sampling distribution* - which with a normal mean estimator sampling distribution gives the t-distribution for a studentised mean estimator.

given i.i.d. data $X_1, \dots, X_n \sim \mathcal{N}(\mu, \sigma^2)$:

$$s^2 = \frac{1}{n-1} \sum_{i=1}^n (x_i - \bar{x})^2 \quad (\text{sample variance})$$

$$\frac{(n-1)s^2}{\sigma^2} \sim \chi_{n-1}^2 \quad \therefore \boxed{s^2 \sim \frac{\sigma^2}{n-1} \chi_{n-1}^2}$$

$$\therefore s_1^2 \sim \frac{\sigma_1^2}{n_1-1} \chi_{n_1-1}^2 \quad \text{and} \quad s_2^2 \sim \frac{\sigma_2^2}{n_2-1} \chi_{n_2-1}^2 \quad (\text{sample variance sampling distributions})$$

Lets now look at the $V = \frac{s_1^2}{n_1} + \frac{s_2^2}{n_2}$ term which is both:

- the variance of the mean difference estimate
- in the denominator of the test statistic

Noting for a chi-squared distribution we have mean of $\mathbb{E}[\chi_\nu^2] = \nu$ and variance of $\text{Var}(\chi_\nu^2) = 2\nu$:

Variance of $V = \frac{s_1^2}{n_1} + \frac{s_2^2}{n_2}$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Var}\left(\frac{s_1^2}{n_1}\right) &= \text{Var}\left(\frac{1}{n_1} \cdot \frac{\sigma_1^2}{n_1-1} \chi_{n_1-1}^2\right) = \underbrace{\left(\frac{1}{n_1} \cdot \frac{\sigma_1^2}{n_1-1}\right)^2}_{\text{scaling of variance}} \cdot \text{Var}(\chi_{n_1-1}^2) \\ &= \frac{1}{n_1^2} \cdot \frac{\sigma_1^4}{(n_1-1)^2} \cdot 2(n_1-1) \end{aligned}$$

$$\text{so} \quad \text{Var}\left(\frac{s_1^2}{n_1}\right) = \frac{\sigma_1^4}{n_1^2} \cdot \frac{2}{n_1-1} \quad \text{and} \quad \text{Var}\left(\frac{s_2^2}{n_2}\right) = \frac{\sigma_2^4}{n_2^2} \cdot \frac{2}{n_2-1}$$

$$\therefore \text{Var}\left(\frac{s_1^2}{n_1} + \frac{s_2^2}{n_2}\right) = \frac{\sigma_1^4}{n_1^2} \cdot \frac{2}{n_1-1} + \frac{\sigma_2^4}{n_2^2} \cdot \frac{2}{n_2-1}$$

Now remember the Student's t-distribution is a function of the z and chi-squared distribution...

$$t_\nu \sim \frac{Z}{\sqrt{V/\nu}} \quad \text{where } Z \sim N(0,1) \quad \text{and } V \sim \chi_\nu^2$$

We previously calculated the non-standard test statistic (which under H_0 follows a normal distribution with zero mean) as well as a Studentised statistic:

$$\bar{x}_1 - \bar{x}_2 \sim \mathcal{N}\left(0, \frac{\sigma_1^2}{n_1} + \frac{\sigma_2^2}{n_2}\right) \quad (\text{non-standardised}) \quad \frac{\bar{x} - \bar{x}_2}{\sqrt{\frac{s_1^2}{n_1} + \frac{s_2^2}{n_2}}} \sim t_\nu \quad (\text{welch test statistic})$$

notice numerator uses population parameters and denominator uses estimates...

$$\frac{N(0, \frac{\sigma_1^2}{n_1} + \frac{\sigma_2^2}{n_2})}{\sqrt{\frac{s_1^2}{n_1} + \frac{s_2^2}{n_2}}} \quad \text{or} \quad \frac{Z}{\sqrt{\frac{s_1^2}{n_1} + \frac{s_2^2}{n_2}}} / \sqrt{\frac{\sigma_1^2}{n_1} + \frac{\sigma_2^2}{n_2}} = \frac{Z}{\sqrt{W}} \sim t_\nu$$

where $W = \frac{\frac{s_1^2}{n_1} + \frac{s_2^2}{n_2}}{\frac{\sigma_1^2}{n_1} + \frac{\sigma_2^2}{n_2}}$ is a ratio of sample-based variance estimate to the true variance

This is the **Welch-Satterthwaite Approximation!**: $W \approx \chi_\nu^2/\nu \Rightarrow \frac{Z}{\sqrt{W}} \sim t_\nu$... we can now calculate the degrees of freedoms but matching the first and second moments of W to χ_ν^2/ν :

$$\mathbb{E}[W] = \mathbb{E}[\chi_\nu^2]/\nu \quad \text{Var}[W] = \text{Var}[\chi_\nu^2/\nu]$$

The Means of W and $\mathbb{E}[\frac{\chi_\nu^2}{\nu}]$ are equal:

$$\mathbb{E}[W] = \frac{\frac{\sigma_1^2}{n_1} + \frac{\sigma_2^2}{n_2}}{\frac{\sigma_1^2}{n_1} + \frac{\sigma_2^2}{n_2}} = \frac{\nu}{\nu} = 1 \quad \text{2.2 scaling of expectation}$$

Equating Variance of W with $\text{Var}(\frac{\chi_\nu^2}{\nu})$:

$$\text{Var}(W) = \frac{\frac{\sigma_1^4}{n_1^2} \cdot \frac{2}{n_1-1} + \frac{\sigma_2^4}{n_2^2} \cdot \frac{2}{n_2-1}}{\left(\frac{\sigma_1^2}{n_1} + \frac{\sigma_2^2}{n_2}\right)^2} = \frac{1}{\nu^2} 2\nu = \frac{2}{\nu} \quad \text{2.7 scaling of variance}$$

Welch-Satterthwaite Degrees of Freedom Approximation:

From the last equation of variance of W ...

$$\nu = \frac{2 \left(\frac{\sigma_1^2}{n_1} + \frac{\sigma_2^2}{n_2}\right)^2}{\frac{2\sigma_1^4}{n_1^2(n_1-1)} + \frac{2\sigma_2^4}{n_2^2(n_2-1)}}$$

lastly we must simplify and also approximate population variances σ_1 and σ_2 with sample variances...

$$\nu = \frac{\left(\frac{s_1^2}{n_1} + \frac{s_2^2}{n_2}\right)^2}{\frac{s_1^4}{n_1^2(n_1-1)} + \frac{s_2^4}{n_2^2(n_2-1)}}$$

□

1.5 Paired (dependent) t-test

Used for mean comparison on matched samples e.g. before/after measurements or repeated measures on the same subjects. Tests whether the mean of the differences between paired observations is zero. each sample is paired with an associated sample in the second dataset;

- dependent pairs, independent sample
- identically normally distributed (or CTL applies for large n)

(it doesn't assume matching variance)

test statistic:

$$t = \frac{\bar{d}}{s_d/\sqrt{n}} \quad \text{where} \quad \begin{cases} d_i = x_i - y_i \text{ is the paired difference} \\ s_d \text{ is the standard deviation of the differences} \\ \bar{d} \text{ is the mean of the differences} \\ n \text{ number of pairs} \\ \text{the t-statistic is compared against the } n - 1 \text{ t-distribution} \end{cases}$$

standard deviation:

$$s_d = \sqrt{\frac{1}{n-1} \sum_{i=1}^n (d_i - \bar{d})^2}$$

Theorem 1.4. pooled t-test test statistic The pooled t-test statistic is given by:

Proof. For each subject with ordinal $i \in 1, \dots, n$, X_i and Y_i are the paired measurement. The sample of difference is denoted as D_1, D_2, \dots, D_n where $D_i = X_i - Y_i$

- the mean difference is given by $\bar{D} = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n D_i$
- the sample variance of the differences $s_D^2 = \frac{1}{n-1} \sum_{i=1}^n (D_i - \bar{D})^2$

We want to test whether the mean of the differences is zero. Under $H_0 : \mu_1 = \mu_2$ so

$$t_{n-1} \sim \frac{\bar{D} - |\mu_1 - \mu_2|}{s_D/\sqrt{n}} = \frac{\bar{D}}{s_D/\sqrt{n}}$$

□

2 Foundational Statistical Properties

2.1 Expectation of Random Variables

2.1.1 Affine and Linear Combinations of Expectation

Lemma 2.1. Linearity of Expectation. For any random variables X and Y :

$$\mathbb{E}[X + Y] = \mathbb{E}[X] + \mathbb{E}[Y]$$

Continuous case :

Proof. Assume X and Y are continuous random variables with a joint probability density function pdf(q). Then:

$$\begin{aligned}\mathbb{E}[X + Y] &= \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} (x(q) + y(q)) \text{pdf}(q) dq \\ &= \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} x(q) \text{pdf}(q) dq + \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} y(q) \text{pdf}(q) dq \\ &= \mathbb{E}[X] + \mathbb{E}[Y]\end{aligned}$$

□

Discrete case :

Proof. Assume X and Y are discrete with probability mass function pmf(ω_i). Then:

$$\begin{aligned}\mathbb{E}[X + Y] &= \sum_{i=0}^n (x(\omega_i) + y(\omega_i)) \text{pmf}(\omega_i) \\ &= \sum_{i=0}^n x(\omega_i) \text{pmf}(\omega_i) + \sum_{i=0}^n y(\omega_i) \text{pmf}(\omega_i) \\ &= \mathbb{E}[X] + \mathbb{E}[Y]\end{aligned}$$

□

Lemma 2.2. Scaling and Shifting of Expectation. For any random variables X and Y :

$$\mathbb{E}[aX + b] = a\mathbb{E}[X] + b$$

Continuous case :

Proof. Assume X is a continuous random variable with pdf(q) and a and b are scalar constants. Then:

$$\begin{aligned}\mathbb{E}[aX + b] &= \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} (ax(q) + b) \text{pdf}(q) dq \\ &= \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} ax(q) \text{pdf}(q) + b \text{pdf}(q) dq \\ &= a \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} x(q) \text{pdf}(q) dq + b \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \text{pdf}(q) dq \\ &= a\mathbb{E}[X] + b\end{aligned}$$

□

Discrete case :

Proof. Assume X is discrete with pmf(ω_i) and a and b are scalar constants. Then:

$$\begin{aligned}\mathbb{E}[aX + b] &= \sum_{i=0}^n (ax(\omega_i) + b) \text{pmf}(\omega_i) \\ &= \sum_{i=0}^n (ax(\omega_i) \text{pmf}(\omega_i) + b \text{pmf}(\omega_i)) \\ &= a \sum_{i=0}^n x(\omega_i) \text{pmf}(\omega_i) + b \sum_{i=0}^n \text{pmf}(\omega_i) \\ &= a\mathbb{E}[X] + b\end{aligned}$$

□

Corollary 2.3. Difference in Expectation. For any random variables X and Y :

$$\mathbb{E}[X - Y] = \mathbb{E}[X] - \mathbb{E}[Y]$$

Proof. Follows directly from Lemma 2.1 by setting $Y \mapsto -Y$. □

Corollary 2.4. Expectation of Sample Mean. For i.i.d. data x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n with mean μ :

$$\mathbb{E}(\bar{x}) = \mathbb{E}[X] \quad \text{for i.i.d. data non-biased estimator}$$

Proof.

$$\begin{aligned}\bar{x} &= \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n x_i \\ \mathbb{E}[\bar{x}] &= \mathbb{E}\left[\frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n x_i\right] = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n \mathbb{E}[x_i] \quad \text{2.1 and 2.2 linearity \& scaling of expectation} \\ &= \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n \mu = \mu\end{aligned}$$

□

2.2 Variance and Covariance of Random Variables

2.2.1 Shortcut Formula for Variance

Definition 2.5. Computational Formula for Variance (Shortcut Formula). For any random variables X and Y :

$$\text{Var}(X) = \mathbb{E}[X^2] - \mathbb{E}[X]^2$$

Proof.

$$\begin{aligned}\text{Var}(X) &= \mathbb{E}[(X - \mathbb{E}[X])^2] \\ &= \mathbb{E}[X^2 - 2X\mathbb{E}[X] + (\mathbb{E}[X])^2] \\ &= \mathbb{E}[X^2] - 2\mathbb{E}[X]\mathbb{E}[X] + (\mathbb{E}[X])^2 \quad \text{(2.1 linearity of expectation)} \\ &= \mathbb{E}[X^2] - \mathbb{E}[X]^2\end{aligned}$$

□

2.2.2 Affine and Linear Combinations of Variance

Definition 2.6. bilinearity of covariance (definition of covariance via expectation)

For any random variables X and Y :

$$\text{Cov}(X, Y) = \mathbb{E}[XY] - \mathbb{E}[X]\mathbb{E}[Y]$$

Proof. Starting with the definition of covariance and using the linearity of expectation 2.1:

$$\begin{aligned}\text{Cov}(X, Y) &\equiv \mathbb{E}[(X - \mathbb{E}[X])(Y - \mathbb{E}[Y])] \\ &= \mathbb{E}[XY - X\mathbb{E}[Y] - \mathbb{E}[X]Y + \mathbb{E}[X]\mathbb{E}[Y]] \\ &= \mathbb{E}[XY] - \mathbb{E}[X]\mathbb{E}[Y] - \mathbb{E}[X]\mathbb{E}[Y] + \mathbb{E}[X]\mathbb{E}[Y] \quad \text{(2.1 linearity of expectation)} \\ &= \mathbb{E}[XY] - \mathbb{E}[X]\mathbb{E}[Y]\end{aligned}$$

□

Lemma 2.7. *shifting and scaling of variance* For any random variable X and scalar constants a, b :

$$\text{Var}(aX + b) = a^2 \text{Var}(X)$$

Proof. Let $\mu = \mathbb{E}[X]$, from 2.2 scaling and shifting of expectation $\mathbb{E}[aX + b] = a\mu + b$ then:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Var}(aX + b) &= \mathbb{E}[(aX + b - [a\mu + b])^2] \\ &= \mathbb{E}[(aX - a\mu)^2] \\ &= \mathbb{E}[a^2(X - \mu)^2] \\ &= a^2\mathbb{E}[(X - \mu)^2] \quad (2.2 \text{ scaling of expectation}) \\ &= a^2 \text{Var}(X) \end{aligned}$$

□

Lemma 2.8. *variance of a linear combination* For any random variable X and scalar constants a, b :

$$\text{Var}(X + Y) = \text{Var}(X) + \text{Var}(Y) + 2 \text{Cov}(X, Y)$$

Proof.

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Var}(X + Y) &= \mathbb{E}[(X + Y)^2] - (\mathbb{E}[X + Y])^2 \quad (2.5 \text{ computational formula for variance}) \\ &= \mathbb{E}[X^2 + 2XY + Y^2] - (\mathbb{E}[X] + \mathbb{E}[Y])^2 \end{aligned}$$

by 2.1 linearity of expectation...

$$\begin{aligned} &= \mathbb{E}[X^2] + 2\mathbb{E}[XY] + \mathbb{E}[Y^2] - (\mathbb{E}[X]^2 + 2\mathbb{E}[X]\mathbb{E}[Y] + \mathbb{E}[Y]^2) \\ &= (\mathbb{E}[X^2] - \mathbb{E}[X]^2) + (\mathbb{E}[Y^2] - \mathbb{E}[Y]^2) + 2(\mathbb{E}[XY] - \mathbb{E}[X]\mathbb{E}[Y]) \end{aligned}$$

from 2.5 computational formula for variance and 2.6 bilinearity of covariance...

$$= \text{Var}(X) + \text{Var}(Y) + 2 \text{Cov}(X, Y)$$

□

Corollary 2.9. *Variance of Difference for Independent Variables.* For any random variables X and Y :

$$\text{Var}(X - Y) = \text{Var}(X) + \text{Var}(Y) \quad \text{for independent variables}$$

Lemma 2.10. *variance of expectation* For any random variable X and scalar constants a, b :

$$\text{Var}(\bar{X}) = \frac{\sigma^2}{n} \quad (\text{for known population parameters})$$

Proof. Let X_1, X_2, \dots, X_n be n i.i.d. random variables where $\mathbb{E}[X_i] = \mu$ and $\text{Var}(X_i) = \sigma^2$:

$$\begin{aligned}\text{Var}(\bar{X}) &= \text{Var}\left(\frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n X_i\right) \\ &= \frac{1}{n^2} \text{Var}\left(\sum_{i=1}^n X_i\right) \quad (\text{scaling } \text{Var}(aX) = a^2 \text{Var}(X)) \\ &= \frac{1}{n^2} \sum_{i=1}^n \text{Var}(X_i) \quad (\text{linearity and independence}) \\ &= \frac{1}{n^2} \cdot n\sigma^2 = \frac{\sigma^2}{n}\end{aligned}$$

□

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